

Applying a Functional Size Measurement Procedure for Defect Detection in MDD Environments

Beatriz Marín, Giovanni Giachetti, and Oscar Pastor

Centro de Investigación en Métodos de Producción de Software,
Universidad Politécnica de Valencia,
Camino de Vera s/n, 46022 Valencia, Spain
{bmarin,ggiachetti,opastor}@pros.upv.es

Abstract. Nowadays, it is widely accepted that functional size measurement is essential to manage and control software projects. In order to obtain early indicators for software projects, many functional size measurement procedures have been developed to measure the functional size of conceptual models. To do this, the measurement procedures assume that models do not present defects. However, this is an unreal assumption because, in practice, the conceptual models can have defects that may affect the implementation of final applications. This is especially important for software production processes based on MDD technology, where the conceptual models are key artifacts used as inputs in the process of code generation. Therefore, this paper presents how a functional size measurement procedure (which has been developed for the measurement of conceptual models of a specific MDD environment) can help in the detection of defects in conceptual models.

Keywords: Conceptual Model, Functional Size, Measurement Procedure, COSMIC, Model-Driven Development, Defect Detection.

1 Introduction

During the last few years, software production processes have evolved from the solution space (software product) to the problem space (conceptual models). Models are abstractions of the reality that help to understand complex problems and their potential solutions [34]. Thus, Model-Driven Development (MDD) methods have been emerged to take advantage of the benefits of the use of models, such as a simplified view of the problem (using concepts that are much less bound to the underlying implementation technology and are much closer to the problem domain); and an easy way to specify, understand, and maintain the systems.

In a software production process based on MDD technology, the conceptual models are key artifacts that are used as input in the process of code generation. These conceptual models must provide a holistic view of all the components of the final application (including the structure of the system, the behavior, the interaction between the users and the system, etc.) in order to be able to automatically generate the final application. To do this, the models (conceptual models) must have enough semantic formalization to specify all the functionality of the final application and also to avoid

different interpretations for the same model. Therefore, it is very important to be able to evaluate and improve the quality of the conceptual models in order to improve the quality of the software products generated by using MDD technologies.

One important quality issue to be evaluated is the amount of defects that the conceptual models used in MDD environments can have. In many cases, the defect detection is performed by the MDD compilers, which presents disadvantages such as the extra complexity included in the compiler, and also the identification of defects with regard to specific technical platforms (i.e. Java, C#, etc.). To overcome the limitations of the defect detection procedures embedded in MDD compilers, it is necessary a defect detection procedure that can be applied directly in the conceptual models. Taking into account that in terms of the management of software projects: (1) it is widely accepted that is essential to know the functional size of applications in order to successfully apply estimation models, effort models, and budget models [26], and (2) the measurement of the functional size in conceptual models allows the project leader to generate indicators in early stages of the development cycle of a software product; we advocate the use of a measurement procedure to detect defects in early stages of the software product. Thus, the aim of this work is to present how a functional size measurement procedure that allows the measurement of conceptual models can help in the detection of defects that can have the conceptual models used in MDD environments.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a brief background and a set of relevant related works. Section 3 presents the functional size measurement procedure for the conceptual model of a specific MDD approach that is used to apply the introduced ideas into practical settings. Section 4 presents how a measurement procedure can be used to identify types of defects of the conceptual models. Finally, Section 5 presents some conclusions and points out future work.

2 Background and Related Work

The ISO/IEC 14143-1 [11] standard defines *functional size* as the size of the software derived by quantifying the functional user requirements. This standard also defines a Functional Size Measurement (FSM) as the process of measuring the functional size. In addition, this standard defines a FSM method as the implementation of a FSM that is defined by a set of rules, which is defined in accordance with the mandatory features defined in the ISO/IEC 14143-2 [12].

In order to measure the functional size of software applications, four measurement methods have been recognized as standards: IFPUG FPA [18], MK II FPA [19], NESMA FPA [20], and COSMIC FFP [17]. The first three methods are based on the Function Point Analysis proposal [3]. These FPA-based methods have several limitations for the correct measurement of systems: for instance, they only consider the functionality of the system that the human user observes, they have units that are hard to understand; they do not consider the functionality that allows communication between layers in systems with a layer-based architecture, etc. To overcome the limitations of FPA-based measurement methods, the COSMIC measurement method was defined as the second generation of functional size measurement methods. COSMIC uses a mathematical function to aggregate the functional size of the functional processes specified in the conceptual models and is not limited by maximum values to

measure the size of conceptual models: this helps to better distinguish the size of large conceptual models.

Currently, there are some approaches that apply COSMIC in order to estimate the functional size of future software applications from the requirement models, such as [4]. However, these models do not have enough semantic expressiveness to specify all the functionality of involved systems. There are other proposals designed to measure the functional size of conceptual models, which have more functional expressiveness than requirement models and are used to the automatic generation of final applications. This is the case of Diab's proposal [7] and Poels' proposal [33]. Diab's proposal presents a measurement procedure to measure real time applications modeled with the ROOM language [35]. Poels' proposal presents a measurement procedure to object-oriented applications of the domain of Management Information Systems (MIS) that are modeled with an event-based method called MERODE [6]. Other FSM procedures (based on COSMIC) to measure the functional size of conceptual models can be found in the survey presented in [25].

Summarizing, none of the proposals of measurement procedures based on COSMIC allows an accurately measurement of the functional size of MIS applications from the related conceptual models. Moreover, none of them take into account the improvements made to the COSMIC measurement method, for instance, the capability to measure the functional size of a piece of software of the application depending on the functionality that needs other piece of software. The main limitation of the approaches presented above comes from the lack of expressiveness of the conceptual models that are involved in the generation of the final application, for instance, the conceptual models do not allow the specification of presentation aspects. For this reason, we have selected the OO-Method approach as the reference MDD environment. The OO-Method approach is an object-oriented method that puts the MDA technology in practice [31], separating the business logic from the platform technology, allowing the automatic generation of final applications by means of well-defined model transformations [32]. It provides the semantic formalization needed to define complete and unambiguous conceptual models, allowing the specification of all the functionality of the final application at conceptual level. This method has been implemented in an industrial tool [4] that allows the automatic generation of fully working applications. The applications generated can be desktop or web MIS applications and can be generated in several technologies (for instance, java, C#, visual basic, etc.). In the next section we present a measurement procedure that is based on this MDD approach.

3 A FSM Procedure for Conceptual Models of an MDD Approach

OOmCFP (OO-Method COSMIC Function Points) [23] is a measurement procedure that was developed for measuring the functional size of the applications generated by the OO-Method MDD environment. The OOmCFP procedure measures the functional size focusing on the conceptual model of the OO-Method MDD approach, which is comprised of an object model, a functional model, a dynamic model, and a presentation model.

The OOmCFP measurement procedure was defined in accordance with the COSMIC measurement manual version 3.0 [2]. Given that the OOmCFP procedure was designed in accordance with COSMIC, a mapping between the concepts used in COSMIC and

the concepts used in the OO-Method conceptual model has been defined [22]. The OOmCFP FSM procedure is structured in the three phases of the COSMIC method: the strategy phase, the mapping phase, and the measuring phase.

With respect to the *strategy phase*, the scope of the measurement can be determined by the functional processes, the layers, or the whole application. Since the OOMethod applications are generated with a three tier architecture (presentation, logic, and database), each tier of the architecture is associated with the other tiers in a superior/subordinate hierarchical dependency. Therefore, the presentation tier can use the services of the logic tier because the logic tier is beneath the presentation tier in the hierarchy. In the same way, the logic tier can use the services of the database tier because the database tier is beneath the logic tier in the hierarchy. Thus, the layers correspond to the hierarchical tiers of the OO-Method applications: the presentation tier, the logic tier, and the database tier.

In addition, the OO-Method applications have at least one software component in each tier of the architecture: the client component, the server component, and the database component. For this reason, the pieces of software correspond to the software components: the client component, the server component, and the database component. Finally, the users are the human users, the client component, and the server component of the applications. The users are separated from the pieces of software by a boundary.

With respect to the *mapping phase*, the functional processes are groups of functionality that can be directly accessed by the users. These groups of functionality correspond to the interaction units specified in the menu of the presentation model. The data groups correspond to the classes of the object model that participate in the functional processes. The data attributes correspond to the attributes of the classes identified as data groups.

With regard to the *measuring phase*, the data movements correspond to the movements of data groups between the users and the functional processes. Each functional process has two or more data movements. Each data movement moves a single data group. A data movement can be an Entry (E), an Exit (X), a Read (R), or a Write (W) data movement. This proposal has 29 rules to identify the data movements that can occur in the OO-Method applications. Each rule is structured with a concept of the COSMIC measurement method, a concept of the OO-Method approach, and the cardinalities that associate these concepts. The rules for the data movements can be visualized in [22]. These mapping rules detect the data movements (E, X, R, and W) of all the functionality needed for the correct operation of the generated application, which must be built by the developer of the application. Finally, this proposal has a set of rules to obtain the functional size of each functional process of the application, of each piece of software of the application, and of the whole application.

Therefore, the OOmCFP procedure has been designed to obtain accurate measures of the applications that are generated from the OO-Method conceptual model. This is feasible because we have selected a conceptual model that has enough semantic expressiveness to specify all the functionality of the final application (the conceptual model of the OO-Method MDD approach). Thus, the measures obtained are accurate because all the data movements that occur in the final application could be traceable to the conceptual model. This measurement procedure has been automated, providing the measurement results in a few minutes and using minimal resources [24]. However, the OOmCFP measurement procedure assumes that the conceptual model has high quality, that is, the OOmCFP procedure assumes that the conceptual model is correct, complete,

and without defects. Obviously, this is an unreal assumption because several times the conceptual models present defects. In the following section we discuss this issue in order to use the measurement procedure to improve the quality of the conceptual models.

4 Improving the Quality of Conceptual Models Using a FSM Procedure

In the literature, there is no consensus for the definition of quality of conceptual models. There are several proposals that use different terminology to refer to the same concepts. There are also many proposals that do not even define what they mean by quality of conceptual models. In order to achieve consensus about the definition of quality of conceptual models and then improve the quality of these kind of models, we have adopted the definition proposed by Moody [29]. This definition is based on the definition of quality of a product or service in the ISO 9000 standard [10]. Therefore, we understand the quality of a conceptual model to be *“The total of features and characteristics of a conceptual model that bear on its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs”*.

To evaluate the quality of software products, the ISO 9126 standard [13] has been defined. This standard defines a set of characteristics and sub-characteristics that are oriented to evaluate the quality of software products from three perspectives: the internal quality of software products [15], the external quality of software products [14], and the quality in use of software products [16]. However, since the ISO 9126 standard has been illustrated in the evaluation of the quality of final applications, it is necessary to select the characteristics, sub-characteristics and metrics that can be applied to the conceptual models in order to evaluate their quality.

In the last few years, several proposals have emerged to evaluate the quality of conceptual models based on the ISO 9126 standard: for instance, Genero et al., Li and Henry, Lorenz and Kidd, Bansiya and Davis, Chidamber and Kemerer, etc. A detailed description of these proposals can be found in [21]. These proposals focus on the evaluation of the maintainability of conceptual models [21]. In addition, there are also proposals that attempt to evaluate the usability of software products in the conceptual models, for instance, Panach et al. [30], and Abrahao et al. [1]. Despite the great number of proposals that present metrics to evaluate the internal quality of conceptual models, none of the proposals has performed an analysis of the defect types that can be identified in conceptual models, and the conceptual constructs that must be measured in order to achieve quality characteristics in the conceptual model.

Defect detection refers to find anomalies in software products in order to correct them and, therefore, obtain software products of better quality. The IEEE 1044 standard classification for software anomalies [9] define an anomaly as *any condition that deviates from expectations based on requirements specifications, design documents, user documents, standards, etc. or from someone’s perceptions or experiences*. This definition is very broad, so that different persons can found different anomalies in the same software artifact, and even the anomalies that found one person could be don’t perceived as anomalies for other person. This situation has caused that many researchers redefine the concepts of error, defect, failure, fault, etc.; and that many times these concepts have been used indistinctly [8]. In order to avoid the proliferation of concepts

related to the software anomalies, in this paper we analyze the proposals of defect detection in conceptual models adapting the terminology defined by Meyer in [27]:

- Error: It is a wrong decision made during the development of a conceptual model.
- Defect: It is a property of a conceptual model that may cause the model to depart from its intended behavior.
- Fault: It is the event of a software system departing from its intended behavior during one of its executions.

Taking into account that the costs of faults correction increase exponentially over the development life cycle [29], it is of paramount importance to discover faults as early as possible, which means detect errors or defects. The next section shows how a measurement procedure can be used to identify defects in the conceptual models.

4.1 Using the OOmCFP Measurement Procedure to Detect Defects

Since the measurement of the functional size using the OOmCFP approach has defined rules to perform the mapping between the concepts of COSMIC and OO-Method, and rules to identify the data movements of the final application in the conceptual model; it is possible to identify some defects that impede the compilation of the conceptual model or that cause faults in the generated application.

The main concepts of the models that comprise the OO-Method conceptual model are well-known because they are the same as those used in the UML diagrams [10]. However, for a better understanding of the defects that can be identified, the OOMethod models and their conceptual constructs (which are used by OOmCFP) are briefly described in the following paragraphs.

The object model of the OO-Method approach describes the static part of the system. This model allows the specification of classes, attributes, derived attributes, events, transactions, operations, preconditions, integrity constraints, agents, and relationships between classes. In this model, the *agents* are active classes that can access specific attributes of the classes of the model and that can execute specific services of the classes of the model.

The functional model of the OO-Method approach allows the specification of the effects that the execution of an event has over the value of the attributes of the class that owns the event by means of a *valuation formula*.

The presentation model allows the specification of the graphical user interface of an application in an abstract way [28]. To do this, the presentation model has a set of abstract presentation patterns that are organized hierarchically in three levels: access structure, interaction units, and auxiliary patterns. The first level allows the specification of the system access structure. Based on the menu-like view provided by the first level, the second level allows the specification of the interaction units of the system. The interaction units are groups of functionality that allow the users of the application to interact with the system. Thus, the interaction units of the interaction model represent entry-points for the application, and they can be:

- A *Service Interaction Unit* (SIU). This interaction unit represents the interaction between a user of the application and the execution of a system service.
- A *Population Interaction Unit* (PIU). This interaction unit represents the interaction with the system that deals with the presentation of a set of instances of a class.
- An *Instance Interaction Unit* (IIU). This interaction unit represents the interaction with an object of the system.
- The three previous elementary interaction units can be composed to build a *Master Detail Interaction Unit* (MDIU).

The third level of the presentation model allows the specification of the auxiliary patterns that characterize lower level details about the behavior of the interaction units. These auxiliary patterns are: entry, selection list, arguments grouping, masks, filters, actions, navigations, order criteria, and display set. The *display set* pattern is used to specify which attributes of a class or its related classes will be shown to the user in a PIU or an IIU.

Table 1 lists a set of rules of the OOmCFP measurement procedure that are related to the mapping between COSMIC and OO-Method, and how these rules help to find defect in the conceptual models.

Table 1. Mapping Rules of OOmCFP

COSMIC	OO-Method	Defects
Functional User	<u>Rule 1:</u> Identify 1 functional user for each agent in the OO-Method object model.	<u>Defect 1:</u> An object model without a specification of an agent class.
Functional Process	<u>Rule 5:</u> Identify 1 functional process for each interaction unit that can be directly accessed in the menu of the OO-Method presentation model.	<u>Defect 2:</u> An OO-Method Conceptual Model without a definition of the presentation model. <u>Defect 3:</u> A presentation model without the specification of one or more interaction units.
Data Group	<u>Rule 6:</u> Identify 1 data group for each class defined in the OO-Method object model, which does not participate in an inheritance hierarchy.	<u>Defect 4:</u> An object model without the specifications of one or more classes. <u>Defect 5:</u> A class without a name. <u>Defect 6:</u> Classes with a repeated name.
Attributes	<u>Rule 9:</u> Identify the set attributes of the classes defined in the OO-Method object model.	<u>Defect 7:</u> A class without the definition of one or more attributes. <u>Defect 8:</u> A class with attributes with repeated names.

Based on the Conradi et al. proposal [5], we classify the defect types into: Omission (missing item), Extraneous information (information that should not be in the model), Incorrect fact (misrepresentation of a fact), Ambiguity (unclear concept), or Inconsistency (disagreement between representations of a concept). Thus, Defects 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 correspond to *omissions*; Defect 5 corresponds to an *incorrect fact*; and Defects 6 and 8 correspond to *ambiguities*.

Table 2 lists a set of rules of the OOmCFP measurement procedure that are related to the identification of data movements. This table also indicates how the presented rules help to find defect in the conceptual models.

Table 2. Rules to identify the data movements of OOmCFP

OO-Method Conceptual Element	OOmCFP Rules	Defects
Display Pattern	<p><u>Rule 10:</u> Identify 1X data movement for the client piece of software for each display pattern in the interaction units that participate in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 9:</u> An instance interaction unit without display pattern. <u>Defect 10:</u> A population interaction unit without display pattern.</p>
	<p><u>Rule 11:</u> Identify 1E data movement for the client piece of software, and 1X and 1R data movements for the server piece of software for each different class that contributes with attributes to the display pattern.</p>	<p><u>Defect 11:</u> A display pattern without attributes.</p>
	<p><u>Rule 13:</u> Identify 1R data movement for the server piece of software for each different class that is used in the effect of the derivation formula of derivate attributes that appear in the display pattern.</p>	<p><u>Defect 12:</u> Derived attributes without a derivation formula.</p>
Filter Pattern	<p><u>Rule 16:</u> Identify 1R data movement for the server piece of software for each different class that is used in the filter formula of the filter patterns of the interaction units that participate in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 13:</u> A filer without a filter formula.</p>
Service	<p><u>Rule 20:</u> Identify 1R data movement for the server piece of software for each different class that is used in the effect of the valuation formula of events that participate in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 14:</u> An event of a class of the object diagram without valuations.</p>
	<p><u>Rule 21:</u> Identify 1W data movement for the server piece of software for each create event, destroy event, or event that has valuations (represented by the class that contains the service) that participate in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 15:</u> A class without a creation event.</p>
	<p><u>Rule 22:</u> Identify 1R data movement for the server piece of software for each different class that is used in the service formula of transactions, operations, or global services that participate in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 16:</u> Transactions without a specification of a sequence of services (service formula). <u>Defect 17:</u> Operations without a specification of a sequence of services (service formula). <u>Defect 18:</u> Global services without a specification of a sequence of services (service formula).</p>

Table 2. (continued)

<p><u>Rule 23:</u> Identify 1E data movement and 1X data movement for the client piece of software, and 1E data movement for the server piece of software for the set of data-valued arguments of the services (represented by the class that contains the service) that participate in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p> <p><u>Rule 24:</u> Identify 1E data movement and 1X data movement for the client piece of software, and 1E data movement for the server piece of software for each different object-valued argument of the services that participate in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 19:</u> A service without arguments.</p> <p><u>Defect 20:</u> A service with arguments with repeated names.</p>
<p><u>Rule 31:</u> Identify 1R data movement for the server piece of software for each different class that is used in the precondition formulas of the services that participate in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 21:</u> A precondition without the specification of the precondition formula.</p>
<p><u>Rule 32:</u> Identify 1X data movement for the client piece of software for all error messages of the precondition formulas of the services that participate in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 22:</u> A precondition without an error message.</p>
<p><u>Rule 34:</u> Identify 1R data movement for the server piece of software for each different class that is used in the integrity constraint formulas of the class that contains each service that participates in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 23:</u> An integrity constraint without the specification of the integrity formula.</p>
<p><u>Rule 35:</u> Identify 1X data movement for the client piece of software for all error messages of the integrity constraint formula of the class that contains each service that participates in the interaction units contained in a functional process.</p>	<p><u>Defect 24:</u> An integrity constraint without an error message.</p>

The list of defect types presented in Table 2 also have been classified using the Conradi et al. [5] classification. Thus, Defects 9, 10, 15, 19, 22, and 24 correspond to *omissions*; Defects 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 21, and 23 correspond to an *incorrect fact*; and Defect 20 corresponds to an *ambiguity*. Therefore, we can state that the OOmCFP measurement procedure helps in the identification of defects types of conceptual models, which are related to omissions, incorrect facts, and ambiguities.

It is important to note that Defects 1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 21, and 23 allow the definition of measures that contribute to the evaluation of the sub-characteristic of *compliance* of the conceptual models (in accordance with the ISO 9126 standard), because it is possible to determine if the conceptual model is adhered to the rules and conventions of the model compiler. In the same way, Defects 3, 11, 15, 20, 22, and 24 allow the definition of measures that contribute to the evaluation of the sub-characteristic of *analyzability* of software products (in accordance with the ISO 9126 standard), because it is possible to diagnostic the possible faults of the final application in the conceptual models.

4.2 General Comments

For many years, software industry has applied different techniques for the requirement modeling and definition of conceptual models in order to identify and correct software defects. Otherwise, these defects could propagate to later development phases, which imply an extra cost to fix them. This situation is also present in the new software production processes, such as MDD methods. Therefore, it is very important to use different techniques in order to found defects in the conceptual models, avoiding their propagation to the final application. The use of a unique technique to found defects does not guarantee that all the defects be found. Thus, it is recommended that organizations use several verification techniques [36].

Since in MDD approaches the quality of conceptual models has a direct impact in the quality of generated applications, the use of the OOmCFP measurement procedure for defects detection provides a new technique to improve the quality of conceptual models, and hence, the quality of final applications.

The defect types presented in sub-section 4.1 where identified by applying the OOmCFP FSM procedure to five different case studies of the OO-Method approach, which correspond to a publishing system, a rent-a-car system, an invoice system, a camping system, and a photography agency system. These five case studies have been selected because they (all together) cover all the modeling possibilities of the OOMethod approach. However, it is important to perform controlled experiments to compare our results with the results obtained from other subjects in order to complete the list of defects that can be identified using the OOmCFP measurement procedure.

In addition, the OOmCFP measurement procedure has a tool that automates its application. Therefore, this tool can be adapted to automatically report the defects that may have the conceptual models, and, once the model is free of defects, to obtain the functional size of the final application. This helps to demonstrate that the OOmCFP measurement procedure is not based on an unreal assumption, and that it could really help in the quality improvement of conceptual models used in software projects.

With regard to the generalization of this approach, in spite of the OOmCFP measurement procedure has been developed for a specific MDD environment (called OOMethod), many of the conceptual constructs used in the conceptual model of this environment can be found in other object-oriented MDD approaches, specially in those oriented to the development of management information systems. Thus, the OOmCFP procedure can be easily generalized to other MDD approaches.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented the applicability of the COSMIC standard method to perform the detection of defects of object-oriented conceptual models used in MDD environments. This identification is obtained through the application of a FSM procedure (called OOmCFP), which allows the measurement of functional size from conceptual models related to an MDD approach called OO-Method. This approach has been selected because it allows the whole specification of the final application in a conceptual level, and because it has been successfully applied to industrial software development.

The application of the OOmCFP measurement procedure to shows how the COSMIC specification can be applied in the defects detection is precisely the main contribution of this paper, since this approach can be used for other MDD proposals as reference to improve the quality of their generated applications.

As future work, we plan to complete the definition of a list of defect types that may be introduced in object-oriented conceptual models, and the evaluation in use (by means of empirical studies) of the application of the OOmCFP measurement procedure for the detection of these defects. This also implies the reengineering of the tool that automates the OOmCFP procedure in order to automate the detection of defects.

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